

POLAROGRAPHIC STUDY OF METAL ION COMPLEXES WITH GLOBIN.
PART II*. COBALT, NICKEL, ZINC, AND CADMIUM AT pH 5.0 AND 6.6

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Polarograms of Co, Ni, Zn, and Cd at various concentrations (0.0075-0.02 M) in presence of globin at pH 5.0 and at 37° show that the diffusion currents in presence of 1.0% globin are less than that in 0.01%, leading to the conclusion that the metal ions form complexes with globin, the -COOH groups of which ionise between pH 2.0 and 5.5. In presence of 1.0% globin the diffusion current decreases with time and is constant after 75 minutes in case of Co, Ni, and Zn and 60 minutes in case of Cd. The number of g. atoms of each metal combined with one g. molecule of globin has been calculated. The maximum number of metal atoms combined with one molecule of globin is found to be 24 in the case of Zn; 20 atoms of the bivalent metal are accounted for 40 -COOH and 4 for 8 -SH groups present in one molecule of globin. Lower values at different concentrations of other metals may be attributed to the ionisation of protein-bound metal.

At pH 6.6, under the same conditions as mentioned above, the number of g.atoms of Co, Ni, Zn, and Cd combined with one g.molecule of globin has been found to be 18 to 20. Since the imidazole group ionises between pH 6.0 and 8.0, it is presumed that there are maximum 40 histidine residues in one molecule of globin.

Polarograms of Co^{2+} and Ni^{2+} ions in presence of 1.0% globin solution at pH 6.6 and at 37° were studied by the authors previously (*J. Univ. Bombay*, 1958, 26, Part II, 15) and the metal ions were found to react with globin, combination taking place at the imidazole groups of histidine residues, which ionised between pH 6.0 and 8.0. The object of the present work was to study the polarograms of Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , and Cd^{2+} ions in presence of 1.0% globin at pH 5.0 and 6.6 and at 37°. Since imidazole group of histidine residue of the protein does not ionise at pH < 6.0, as shown by Tanford (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 211), the metal ions are expected to replace the H of -COOH groups, which ionise between pH 2.0 and 5.5 according to the same author.

EXPERIMENTAL

The apparatus, general technique and the chemicals used were as described by the authors in Part I (*loc. cit.*). The molecular weight of globin was determined by deducting the amount of heme from the M.W. of hemoglobin (63,136), determined by the authors from the quantity of iron in a weighed portion of hemoglobin; it was found to be 60,672.

Solutions of Co, Ni, Zn, and Cd acetates (E. Merck's C.P.) were prepared and standardised by chemical analysis. pH of the solutions used for polarographic analysis was adjusted with the help of a Cambridge Instrument pH-meter with a glass electrode.

Standard globin solution was prepared from hemoglobin, dissolved in KOH, by the addition of 1.0N-HCl, when heme was precipitated as hemin. The concentration of globin solution, determined approximately from the difference in the weights of hemoglobin used and hemin obtained, was checked by Kjeldahl's method. Optical rotation of the globin solution was found; and knowing the concentration, specific rotation of globin solution was determined, which was used to check the concentration of globin solution prepared for use from time to time. 1.0% Globin solution (40 c.c.) was used every time for the polarographic study.

TABLE IV

Metal ion.	Initial conc. (in presence of 0.01% globin). i_{d_0} .	Half-wave potential.	Final conc. (in presence of 1.0% globin). (i_d)	Decrease in conc. of metal ion. ($i_{d_0} - i_d$)	Amount of metal combined in g. atoms with 0.4g. of globin.	No. of atoms of the metal combined with one molecule of globin.	Degree of ionisation of the complex.	
								(X) $\left[\frac{i_{d_0} - i_d}{F} \times \frac{40}{1000} \right]$
Zn^{2+}	0.0200M	62.2 μ_A	-1.3 volts	52.0 μ_A	10.2 μ_A	1.302×10^{-4}	19.76	0.000
	0.0150	47.0	-1.3	36.8	10.2	1.302×10^{-4}	19.76	0.000
	0.0100	31.4	-1.3	21.4	10.0	1.277×10^{-4}	19.37	0.017
	0.0075	23.6	-1.3	13.8	9.8	1.251×10^{-4}	18.99	0.037
							Mean 19.47	
Cd^{2+}	0.0200	62.5	-0.80	53.0	9.2	1.176×10^{-4}	17.84	0.096
	0.0150	47.0	-0.80	37.9	9.1	1.163×10^{-4}	17.64	0.105
	0.0100	31.2	-0.85	22.2	9.0	1.150×10^{-4}	17.45	0.115
	0.0075	23.5	-0.85	14.6	8.9	1.138×10^{-4}	17.26	0.125
							Mean 17.55	

DISCUSSION

Table I shows that the ratio of the diffusion current (i_{d_0}) to the molar concentration 'C' is constant for a particular ion. This ratio (F) has been utilised to find the metal ion concentration in presence of globin. The value of the product m^3, λ as shown in column 4 of Table I is also nearly constant at the different initial concentrations of the metal ions. This shows that the diffusion current in the electrolytic cell was regular for these concentrations and that the polarometer was working properly. On mixing a solution of globin with that of the acetate of the metal, Co, Ni, Zn or Cd, no precipitate was obtained even on centrifuging.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

Polarograms corresponding to Table II, recorded in Figs. 1-4 (*b*-curves) show that the diffusion currents of Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , and Cd^{2+} ions at pH 5.0 in presence of 1.0% globin are much less than those in case of 0.01% (a-curves). The diffusion current goes on decreasing and remains constant after 75 minutes in the case of Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , and Zn^{2+} and after 60 minutes in case of Cd^{2+} ions, when the reaction is supposed to be complete. The kinetics of the complex formation of Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , and Cd^{2+} ions at pH 5.0 have been studied and will be published in a separate communication. The difference in the values of diffusion currents in presence of 0.01% and 1.0% globin leads to the conclusion that the metal ions are reacting with globin at pH 5.0. According to Tanford (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 441) the $-\text{COOH}$ groups of protein ionise between pH 2.0 and 5.5. So in the above investigation at pH 5.0, the metal ions must have displaced the H atoms of the $-\text{COOH}$ groups of globin. Maximum 24 atoms of a bivalent metal have been found to combine with one molecule of globin at pH 5.0 in case of Zn.

FIG. 3

FIG. 4

Since a bivalent metal will combine at two monovalent groups of globin, which ionise at this pH, there must be maximum 48 such sites of combination. But according to Tristram (vide Rough-ton, "Chemistry and Biology of Proteins: Hemoglobin", Interscience Publishers Inc., New York, 1949, p. 109) there are 70 $-\text{COOH}$ groups in 10^5 g. of horse hemoglobin. So there are 48 $-\text{COOH}$ groups in one molecule of hemoglobin (M.W. 68,000); subtracting from this 8 $-\text{COOH}$ groups of 4 heme residues, one molecule of globin will contain 40 $-\text{COOH}$ groups, which account for 20 atoms of the metal; the remaining 4 may be combining at 8 $-\text{SH}$ groups since there are 8 atoms of sulphur in one molecule of globin. Again, it is observed that the lower the concentration of the metal ions, the less the combination; this may be due to the partial ionisation of the complex formed.

Polarograms recorded in Figs. 5 and 6 (*b*-curves) show that at pH 6.6 the diffusion currents of Zn^{2+} and Cd^{2+} ions in presence of 1.0% globin are less than that in case of 0.01%. It was observed that the diffusion currents in all cases went on decreasing with time and ultimately remained constant after 75 minutes in case of Zn and 60 minutes in case of Cd, thus indicating the gradual combination of Zn^{2+} and Cd^{2+} ions with globin at pH 6.6. The kinetics of the complex

formation of Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , and Cd^{2+} ions at pH 6.6 have been studied and will be published shortly.

FIG. 5

FIG. 6

According to Tanford (*loc. cit.*) the imidazole groups of proteins ionise between pH 6.0 and 8.0. So in the above investigation at pH 6.6, the metal ions must have combined at the imidazole groups of the histidine residues of globin. The identity of the groups on a protein molecule, which bind a species of a metal ion, can sometimes be inferred from the number of sites at which the metal is bound. In the present investigation the authors have found maximum 40 sites in one molecule of globin where metal atoms combine with it at pH 6.6 since Table IV shows that the maximum number of bivalent metal ions that can combine with a globin molecule is 20. The small difference in the number of combined atoms in the case of the two metals, Zn and Cd, and at different concentrations, is attributed to ionisation of the metal-protein complex, which is found to increase with dilution.

According to Tristram (*loc. cit.*) there are 56 imidazole groups in 10^5 g. of horse hemoglobin; from this the number of histidine residues in one molecule of horse hemoglobin (M.W. 68,000), and hence in one molecule of globin, is calculated to be 38. Since the figure 40, determined by the authors by polarographic method, nearly tallies with the above figure 38, as determined by organic chemistry methods, it is concluded that at pH 6.6 the metals, Zn and Cd, must have combined with the imidazole groups of the histidine residues of globin. At pH 6.6 $-\text{COOH}$ groups cannot be active to allow H to be replaced by a metal.

Though the above coincidence of results is observed, yet there can be a plea that the fall in diffusion current in presence of 1.0% globin may be due to decrease in diffusion coefficient owing to increase in viscosity. But it was observed by the authors that the diffusion current in presence of 1.0% globin decreased with time, reaching minimum after 75 minutes in case of Co, Ni, and Zn and 60 minutes in case of Cd; in addition to this it was observed that the rate of fall in the diffusion current increased with the initial concentration of the metal ions. This fact supports the combination of the metal ions with the protein molecules.